

A Dimensional Geometry of Infinity

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Abstract

In this paper we discuss a different method of describing infinity. Traditionally, infinities are handled by non standard analysis, hypereals, dual numbers, transfinite numbers or manipulating limits. However, all these processes fail to highlight the difference between infinities describing different dimensions (e.g: infinite lines, planes e.c.t). We denote an n -dimensional infinite measure as ∞_n . So an infinite line is ∞_1 , an infinite plane is ∞_2 and an infinite volume as ∞_3 , etc. We define some axioms, describing different elements of how our system behaves. We prove a simple model in order to prove that our axioms are not contradictory. In addition, we prove some lemmas, to illustrate the implications of the axioms. Finally, we include a some worked examples with various field of mathematics, in order to build an intuition for how the applications of our system works. This system is similar to Cantor's \aleph system, that uses a subscript to describe differences between infinite sets. However, this difference was the level of countability that the cardinality of an infinite set, rather than a geometric quality.

1 Introduction

Infinity occurs plentifully in mathematics and physics, for example the size of the universe or the amount of force black holes produce. In our case, infinity could describe a n -dimensional space with no boundary- for example a vector subspace. However, in standard mathematics, infinity fails to distinguish between two spaces of different dimensional magnitude. Though non-standard analysis, the hypereal numberline, dual numbers, and other systems of dealing with infinities have solved many problems infinity posed to mathematics, this idea is not discussed.

This system explicitly discusses this , by introducing a subscript to the infinity notation, as a method of introducing more information, and thus making it easier to distinguish between two infinities. Interestingly, we prove that this subscript would be equivalent to an exponent. For example, consider an infinite plane. This plane must be composed of two one dimensional infinities, one for each side-length. Hence, to find the area of this plane, we can multiply the side lengths together, or $\infty_1^2 = \infty^2 = \infty_2$ (as it is still a two dimensional infinity).

The layout of this paper is as follows: first we define and justify axioms. We then form a simple model and verify the axioms against the model, proving that the axioms are internally consistent. Afterwards, we prove some propositions to illustrate some implications of our axioms, before showing some worked examples to build a better intuition

for the applications of our system. Finally, we conclude, and discuss connections to other frameworks of infinity, and an alternate model, in the appendix.

2 Axioms

In this section, we define axioms to rigorously describe our system: We define the set:

$$\Gamma := \{\infty_n | n \in \mathbb{N}\}$$

Axiom 1. *For every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists an infinite n -dimensional space: ∞_n*

We must assume this, for this system (or any geometric system) to have any meaning. For example, if there did exist an n such that the corresponding n -dimensional space did not, then no n -dimensional vectors would exist in that space and the system would collapse.

Axiom 2. *For $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, if $m < n$, then $\infty_m < \infty_n$ in terms of dimensional magnitude.*

This allows us to extend the well ordering principle of the real numbers onto Γ , so that we maintain a concept of dimension (a point has a lower dimension than a line has a lower dimension than a plane).

Axiom 3. *For any finite number $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and any ∞_m , we have*

$$x + \infty_m = \infty_m.$$

This maintains consistency with mainstream frameworks of mathematics such as extended reals, nonstandard analysis and dual numbers. Particularly, the absorptive nature of ∞ .

Axiom 4. *For every finite number x , ∞_1 is larger than x*

This too ensure that infinity's absorptive qualities remain.

Axiom 5. *For all quantities a, b, c (finite or infinite),*

$$ab = ba \quad a + b = b + a \quad a(b + c) = ab + ac \quad abc = a(bc) = (ab)c = (ac)b$$

This simply maintains commutativity, distributivity and associativity, so mathematical functions and operations act as usual. This is because there seems to be no apparent reason why these should not hold.

3 Model

In this section, we prove that the axioms are internally consistent. We do this by creating a model in which every axiom is true. This proves that there exists a situation in which none of the axioms contradict any of the other axioms, meaning that there cannot exist a universe in which they do contradict.

Definition We define α as a mathematical object that describes an infinite space, where the power α is raised to, is equivalent to the dimension that the infinite space occupies. That is:

$$\infty_n = \alpha^n.$$

Such that α^2 would be an infinite area, α^3 would be an infinite volume, e.c.t.

Operations. We define the same rules that apply to ordinary exponent, to apply to α .

$$\alpha^m \cdot \alpha^n = \alpha^{m+n}, \quad (\alpha^m)^n = \alpha^{mn}, \quad \frac{\alpha^n}{\alpha^m} = \alpha^{n-m}$$

When we add a finite number to α^n , the sum remains to be α^n due to additive dominance:

$$x + \alpha^n = \alpha^n \quad x \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Order. As the size of the exponents increase, so does the magnitude of the dimension that the variation of α describes :

$$\alpha < \alpha^2 < \alpha^3 < \dots$$

And any real number is less than α^1 , so $x < \alpha$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$. However, we must carefully note that $\alpha^0 \neq 1$ (a result we will prove later in the paper).

Verification of Axioms.

1. Each α^n exists by definition.
2. If $m < n$, then $\alpha^m < \alpha^n$, which describes our second axiom.
3. Finite numbers are absorbed when added to any infinity, which supports our third axiom.
4. Distributivity still exists as well.

4 Lemmas

Lemma 1

$$\infty_n = \infty^n \quad \text{for every } n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Proof. Recall the α -model from Section 3 where we set

$$\infty := \alpha, \quad \infty_n := \alpha^n$$

and assumed the usual exponent laws for α , in particular $(\alpha^a)^b = \alpha^{ab}$ and $(\alpha^1)^n = \alpha^{1 \cdot n}$.

Then, for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\infty_1^n = (\alpha^1)^n = \alpha^{1 \cdot n} = \alpha^n = \infty_n.$$

Thus $\infty^n = \infty_n$ for every n

corollary we can thus prove the exponent law $a^v \cdot a^u = a^{v+u}$ acting on infinity:

$$\infty_p \cdot \infty_q = \infty_{p+q}$$

proof Since $\infty_n = \infty^n$,

$$\infty_p = \infty^p \text{ and } \infty_q = \infty^q.$$

$$\implies \infty_p \cdot \infty_q = \infty^p \cdot \infty^q$$

and given $a^v \cdot a^u = a^{v+u}$

$$, \infty^p \cdot \infty^q = \infty^{p+q}$$

therefore

$$\infty_p \cdot \infty_q = \infty_{p+q}$$

$$\infty_n + \infty_m = \infty_{\max(m,n)}$$

Proof. let $m, n, k \in \mathbb{N}$

$$m > n$$

$$n + k = m$$

Therefore

$$\infty_m + \infty_n = \infty_{n+k} + \infty_n = \infty_n(\infty_0 + \infty_k) = \infty_n \cdot \infty_k = \infty_{n+k} = \infty_m$$

By distributivity

□

$$\infty_0 \neq 1$$

as it is indeterminate By lemma 1,

$$\infty_0 = \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty_1} \frac{h}{h} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} 1$$

which is indeterminate.

5 Worked Examples

Example 1: Dimensional Multiplication

therefore, by multiplying these infinities:

$$\infty_1 \cdot \infty_2 = \infty_3, \quad \infty_2 \cdot \infty_2 = \infty_4, \quad (\infty_1)^3 = \infty_3.$$

Example 2: Infinite Growth in Calculus

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} x = \infty_1, \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} x^2 = \infty_2, \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} x^3 = \infty_3.$$

Differentiation reduces the dimensional magnitude, further proving how infinity is not a constant:

$$\frac{d}{d\infty_1}(\infty_n) = n\infty_{n-1}$$

Since integration is the inverse of differentiation:

$$\int \infty_n d\infty_1 = \infty_{n+1}.$$

Example 3: Infinite Limits and Series

You can add these infinities together:

$$1 + \infty_1 + \infty_2 + \dots$$

or otherwise:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \infty_n$$

due to infinities absorbing properties, the larger infinities absorb the smaller ones, yielding the value ∞_{∞}

Example 4: Linear Algebra with Infinities

Matrix example:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \infty_1 \\ 2 & \infty_3 & 3 \\ \infty_2 & 1 & \infty_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{v} = \begin{bmatrix} \infty_1 \\ 2 \\ \infty_4 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then multiplying gives:

$$A\mathbf{v} = \begin{bmatrix} \infty_5 \\ \infty_4 \\ \infty_6 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Example 6: Vectors with Infinite Components

let

$$\mathbf{w} = \begin{bmatrix} \infty_1 \\ \infty_2 \\ \infty_3 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \|\mathbf{w}\| = \sqrt{\infty_2 + \infty_4 + \infty_6} = \infty_6$$

5.1 Example 7: Non Exponential Infinities

However, not all numerical expressions can be represented. Generally, our

$$\infty_{\infty} = e^{\infty \ln \infty} \Rightarrow \ln \infty_{\infty} = \infty \ln \infty$$

6 Conclusion

Our system attempts to distinguish between infinities describing different dimensions. We define axioms for our system and a model to prove that our axioms are not contradictory. We then prove lemmas and complete worked examples to build a better intuition for how our system works. Further work on this topic could include a correlation between this system and other types of infinity such as Cantor's aleph system for cardinalities, as well as a stronger application to physics (perhaps to singularities).

7 Appendix

A Other Types of Infinity

A.1 Set-Theoretic Infinity

Cantor created a system for distinguishing the cardinalities of infinite sets with different types of infinity. He described a countable infinity as \aleph_0 , and as the cardinality became less countable, the subscript on alpha increased (i.e $\aleph_1, \aleph_2, \aleph_3 \dots \aleph_\infty$). However, our system deals with geometric infinities, not the countability of a set. Further more, dimension is not typically a quality of a set, but geometric almost always have a dimension. So generally the Aleph system is different from this system.

A.2 Infinities in Projective Geometry

Projective geometry adds points at infinity to close the space of Projective Geometry. This would mean that parallel lines meet at infinity. However, projective geometry generally deals one dimension at a time (particularly focusing on two and three dimensional spaces). For this reason, it can be argued that dimension is not a significant factor of projective geometry;. One the other hand, our system is only relevant when there is a difference in dimensions.

A.3 Infinity in Physics

In physics sometimes infinite measures occur. For example, the concept of a singularity implies an infinite curve in space time, meaning that weight, the force gravity produces, is infinite. Further applications of this system could be in physics to gain more meaningful descriptions.

A.4 Transfinite Numbers

Transfinite numbers describe an order of infinities, but in a much wider sense than with cardinal numbers. Transfinite numbers consider counting the natural numbers (1, 2, 3...) until you reach an infinite, or technically "transfinite", value ω . You then continue counting ($\omega + 1, \omega + 2, \omega + 3 \dots$) until you reach 2ω . After 2ω , you can continue counting by ω 's (i.e : $3\omega, 4\omega, 5\omega \dots$). Until you reach ω^2 . At this point, you can start multiplying by ω , reaching $\omega^3, \omega^4, \omega^5 \dots$. Of course you can keep going with tetration and so on. This is why they are transfinite numbers as opposed to infinite numbers, because even though they describe infinities, there is no absolute infinity as there is in Cantor's cardinal

numbers (\aleph_∞). Also, the set of Transfinite Numbers is larger than the Aleph (ironically by the Aleph system, as set of infinite cardinalities has a one to one correspondence with \mathbb{N} , and so is countable, unlike the Transfinite Set). However, replacing the ∞ variable with ω , we find the set $\{\infty^n | n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is equivalent to $\{\omega^n | w \in \mathbb{N}\}$, which makes sense as ∞ and ω represent similar things.